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GRADUATE SCHOOL
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**A STUDY OF VISUAL SALIENCY FOR FREE-VIEWING
AND TASK-ORIENTED CONDITION**

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A STUDY OF VISUAL SALIENCY FOR FREE-VIEWING AND TASK-ORIENTED
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I hereby declare that all information in this document has been obtained and presented in accordance with academic rules and ethical conduct. I also declare that, as required by these rules and conduct, I have fully cited and referenced all material and results that are not original to this work.

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ABSTRACT

A STUDY OF VISUAL SALIENCY FOR FREE-VIEWING AND TASK-ORIENTED CONDITION

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Visual saliency is a widely studied field in computer science. The visual saliency is a field concerning people's visual attention while seeing visual stimuli, an image or frames in a video sequence, and visual saliency methods aim at estimating people's eye fixations correctly. While humans have a granted and comprehensive sight ability provided by the human visual system (HVS), it is not effortless for visual saliency approaches to catch eye fixation points easily and very accurately. Thus, there may be different visual saliency approaches to handle different types of visual attention, affected by viewing conditions or goals of the viewing. In this thesis, we determine to analyze proposed visual saliency methods for different viewing conditions and different attention types, i.e. bottom-up and top-down. Bottom-up visual attention emerges when people observe visual stimuli freely. Top-down visual attention appears when people view visual stimuli related to the content and the viewer has a goal to consider while viewing the visual stimuli. In the first part of the thesis, we explain our study in which we examine state-of-the-art visual saliency methods for 2D desktop and 3D VR viewing conditions. In the second part of the thesis, we focus on top-down visual attention and integrate visual saliency predictions for different goals of the viewers into a single Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) [1] structure.

Keywords: Visual saliency, Bottom-up saliency, Top-down saliency.

Özet

SERBEST GÖRÜNTÜLEME VE GÖREV GÜDÜMLÜ GÖRSEL DİKKAT-ÇEKERLİK ÇALIŞMASI

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Görsel dikkat-çekerlik bilgisayar bilimlerinde genişçe çalışılan bir konudur. Görsel dikkat-çekerlik insanların görsel bir uyaranı, resim veya bir videonun çerçeveleri, izlerkenki görsel dikkatiyle alakalıdır ve görsel dikkat-çekerlik metotları insanların bakış sabitlemelerini doğru tahmin etmeyi hedefler. İnsanların insan görsel sistemi tarafından halihazırda, kapsamlı görü kabiliyetleri varken, dikkat-çekerlik yaklaşımları için bakış sabitlemelerini çabasız ve doğruca yakalamak kolay değildir. Bu sebeple, görüntüleme şartları veya görüntüleme amaçlarından etkilenen farklı görsel dikkat çeşitleri için farklı görsel dikkat-çekerlik yaklaşımları olabilir. Bu tezde, sunmuş görsel-dikkat çekerlik metotlarını farklı görüntüleme şartları ve farklı dikkat tipleri, örn.: alttan-tepeye, tepeden-alta, için analiz etmeyi amaçladık. Alttan-tepeye görsel dikkat görsel uyaranın amaçsızca göz gezdirilmesidir. Tepden-alta görsel dikkat görsel uyarın içerikle alakalıdır ve izleyicinin uyaranı izlerken dikkate aldığı bir amacı vardır. Bu tezin ilk kısmında literatürdeki görsel dikkat-çekerlik metotlarını 2B masa üstü ve 3B sanal gerçeklik görüntüleme şartları için incelediğimiz çalışmamızı detaylandırdık. Tezin ikinci aşamasında tepeden-alta görsel dikkate ve izleyicilerin farklı amaçları için dikkat-çekerlik tahminlerini tek bir Üretici Çekişmeli Ağ yapısına [1] entegre etmeye odaklandık.

Keywords: Görsel dikkat-çekerlik, Alttan-tepeye dikkat-çekerlik, Tepeden-alta dikkat çekerlik.

To my family

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

2D	2 Dimensional
3D	3 Dimensional
ACSD	Anisotropic Center-Surround Difference
AUC	Area Under the Curve
BMS	Boolean Map Saliency
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network(s)
CC	Pearson's Linear Coefficient
csc	Center Surround Connections
eDN	Ensembles of deep networks
FASA	Fast, Accurate, and Size-Aware Salient Object Detection
FCNN	Fully-Connected Neural Networks(s)
FGS	Fine-Grained Saliency
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network
cGAN	Conditional Generative Adversarial Network
HMD	Head-Mounted Display
HVS	Human Visual System
KL	Kullback-Leibler Divergence
LBE	Local Background Enclosure for RGB-D Salient Object Detection
MB	Minimum Barrier Salient Object Detection
MB+	A Variation of Minimum Barrier Salient Object Detection
NSS	Normalized Scanpath Saliency
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic
SIM	Similarity by Histogram Intersection

SVM Support Vector Machine
VR Virtual Reality

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Visual Saliency

The human visual system (HVS) enables us a fast evaluation of complex visual stimuli so that the focus of visual attention to be tuned in conspicuous parts of the visual stimuli with not much of an effort [1, 2]. The visual attention mechanism is studied in the literature comprehensively, yet it remains to be not fully understood, it has several components related to the cognitive, biological, psychological, physical properties of the visual stimuli [3]. Visual saliency is a major topic of the visual attention mechanism. The visual saliency methods yield saliency maps in which the probability of being fixated at each pixel is estimated. The saliency maps take the form of a 2D grey-scale image. Pixels with the probability of one are white, pixels the probability of zero are black and other pixels that have a probability value in the range [0.0-1.0] are mapped to grey-scale values [0-255] in the image. For a computer science viewpoint, visual saliency maps are predicted by algorithms that can use hand-crafted features of the visual stimuli or some features can be learned by training of learning approaches and visual saliency estimation is achieved by using the learned parameters. The visual attention has mainly as two types: bottom-up attention and top-down attention. The bottom-up attention is driven by the properties of the visual scenes regardless of content, whereas the top-down attention is goal-oriented and focuses on what is perceived. Bottom-up attention emerges when people observe visual stimuli freely. In that case, mostly low-level features (like color contrast, depth, motion, centeredness of the objects, etc.) are important for the visual attention mechanism. Top-down attention appears when people view visual stimuli related to the content, like ‘important person in the frame’, ‘where the place is’, ‘what action that the people

in the image are doing' etc. If there is a content-related goal for the viewing act, high-level features (like whether the frame contains people or not, what emotions exist in the frame, etc.) are important for the visual attention mechanism. HVS prioritizes bottom-up visual attention and does not need to make much of an effort, whereas it cannot handle top-down visual attention easily most of the time; initial prioritization usually does not work for the top-down visual attention, it requires more effort and time [4]. The goal of the viewers for top-down attention, the content and type of the visual stimuli, viewing time affect the visual attention. The visual attention can be shaped by the viewing conditions of the visual stimuli. There are different visual saliency approaches for a video sequence type of stimuli and a still image [5] or real-world viewing, monitor viewing, viewing in a Virtual Reality (VR) environment. [6]. The duration of the viewing time also affects the visual attention [7].

There are several studies of visual saliency with both low-level features and high-level features approach. In recent years, most novel studies have used deep learning solutions for both the bottom-up visual attention and top-down visual attention. Deep learning approaches require several samples of data for training so that they can learn and predict attention for test samples. In contrast, there is generally no need for data collection and training for other approaches. On the other hand, the studies that use deep learning mostly outperform traditional image feature-based methods [5, 8]. Within this study, we aim to examine visual saliency methods for different viewing conditions that may be responded diversely by the visual attention mechanism and propose solutions. To this end, we study visual saliency for 2D viewing condition, i.e. viewing 2D via a flat monitor and 3D VR viewing condition, i.e. viewing via VR system with a head-mounted display (HMD), for bottom-up attention, i.e free-viewing and for top-down attention, i.e. goal-oriented viewing. In brief, we initially arrange user study settings so that we collect eye fixation and gaze data of participants while they are viewing provided visual stimuli. For all the different viewing conditions we prepare or directly adopt the visual contents and ask the participants to view the shown visual contents. After data collection, we study different visual saliency methods on collected data regarding different viewing conditions and different attention types. We analyze the results of the saliency methods and make inferences about hand-crafted saliency features in our first study. We get results for GAN based ap-

proaches for our second study. We provide an idea of a single structure to be used in saliency map generation for different goals of top-down attention, we anticipate that the idea can be applied for a mix of different attention types and/or different viewing conditions provided data for all.

1.2 Scope of the Thesis

Within this thesis, we concentrate on finding applicable approaches for visual saliency by considering different viewing conditions. Initially, we conducted our first study to examine free-viewing for 2D and 3D VR with HMD viewing conditions. We prepared video contents for 2D and 3D VR conditions, by using Unity game & simulation engine [9], and collected data from free viewing of the participants of the prepared contents to evaluate and apprehend traditional visual saliency methods that do not use deep learning for these conditions, we consider hand-crafted features to compute visual saliency maps for free-viewing visual attention. We determine to investigate the effects of different features on visual saliency maps. We mainly concentrate on depth map and compare if it is crucial for the visual saliency, especially for 3D VR condition, as implied in some studies [10, 11]. We conclude that it may be crucial but when it is given weight to the depth feature apart from other features, it fails for generating accurate visual saliency maps. Then, we compare 2D and 3D viewing behaviors and find the most appropriate visual saliency method, among the methods that we focus on, for these conditions, especially for 3D VR condition. After our first study, we studied the top-down visual attention. To this end, we define tasks for the participants to perform the given content-related tasks while viewing still image stimuli. We intend to propose a single structure that embraces the saliency map generation for different types of attention. For that purpose, we applied a specific deep learning approach: Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) [12] to handle the visual attention of different tasks at once, in a single network. Since GAN may perform well with fewer data and learns a proper loss function that serving its purpose [12, 13, 14, 15], we opt GAN approach other than other deep learning approaches. Our purpose is to demonstrate that there may be integrated solutions for different viewing conditions and/or different attention types. The main contributions of the thesis are given below:

- We analyze the bottom-up visual attention and visual saliency approaches for different viewing conditions, i.e. 2D and 3D VR viewing conditions.
- We present an eye fixation dataset for top-down visual attention, i.e. different tasks to consider while viewing, and made it publicly available. We examine the viewing behaviors for these different tasks.
- We propose a single network approach that handles different visual saliency tasks. We introduce a GAN-based [12] solution and compare the performance of the two approaches: original approach and integrating multiple discriminators into one network so that we can get results for different viewing conditions, i.e. different tasks, at once.

1.3 Outline of the Thesis

The rest of the chapters are outlined below.

We address related previous works in the literature in chapter 2. By doing that, we provide an insight into the visual saliency concept and different approaches to the concept. We refer to saliency methods for both not using deep learning and using deep learning. We mention commonly adopted features to yield visual saliency maps and different deep learning approaches that automatically extracted the features.

Chapter 3 is the section where we detail our first study. We refer to the visual saliency for free-viewing within 2D and 3D VR viewing conditions. We explain our data collection setting and the results obtained for the collected data.

We elaborate our top-down saliency study in chapter 4. Our user experiment to collect data is described. We share our results for the previous approaches and for the altered version of these approaches proposed in this thesis.

In chapter 5, we draw conclusions by our results and evaluate them with a broader perspective. Based on our results and interpretations, we suggest future lead for improvements.

CHAPTER 2

RELATED WORKS

Visual attention, both bottom-up and top-down attention, is broadly considered in cognitive sciences [1, 4, 16]. The notion of visual saliency is introduced related to the attention processes of the human visual system. Classical visual saliency approaches predict salient, i.e conspicuous, parts of any visual stimuli in order to mimic the visual attention mechanism of HVS [5, 17]. In this section, we introduce visual saliency and its approaches by referring to previous works. Different visual saliency approaches in the literature are referred. We categorize these approaches mainly into two: the visual saliency methods that use hand-crafted features with no learning, and the visual saliency methods that use deep learning. The first category adopts previously used features of the visual stimuli or introduces new features and use them. The second category uses different deep learning approaches [8, 18, 19] most of which are based on Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) layers.

2.1 Hand-Crafted Visual Saliency Models

In the literature, the methods that use hand-crafted features for saliency estimation are mostly inspired by Gestalt principles [20] and some statistical models [5, 21]. These methods may directly use image features such as color, contrast, depth or develop different saliency models such as the bayesian approaches [22, 23, 24], cognitive approaches [25, 26, 27], graph-based approaches [28, 29, 30]. The color feature is often used or altered by the traditional visual saliency methods [31, 32]. Also, several features like color, contrast, texture can be adopted for saliency map generation [33, 34, 35]. There are various visual saliency methods that use hybrid features or

introduce new features [36, 37, 38, 39]. The depth feature is also considered as crucial for the visual saliency [10, 40, 41]. Some of the methods that prioritize the depth feature use RGB-D images [42, 43]. Several further studies introduce and use new features based on depth and benefit the depth feature by weighting the newly introduced depth features [44, 45]. 3D visual saliency may also separately modeled as visual saliency for stereoscopic images [46, 47, 48]. We consider bottom-up attention, i.e. free-viewing, in chapter 3 and we examine visual saliency methods under this category, we prefer the visual saliency methods that employ hand-crafted features for our initial study.

2.2 Deep Learning Approaches for Visual Saliency

Convolutional Neural Networks being successful [49] deliver solutions for different fields of computer vision, as well as the visual saliency field. When deep learning approaches became common for visual saliency solutions, hand-crafted features became less preferable. The main advantage of CNN approaches is that they learn and/or introduce essential features rather than using previously defined hand-crafted features which results in more accurate saliency maps [50, 5]. On the other hand, CNN requires a learning process accompanied by the data to train and computing power which can be considered as a disadvantage. With the advance of hardware capabilities and data access, several deep learning solutions for visual saliency have been developed and used in practice. We refer to some of them in this section.

Ensembles of deep networks (eDN) [51] is the first study that adopts CNN for visual saliency. It performs hyperparameter optimization after a 3-layer network. Then, it benefits the hyperparameter optimization and finds independent models which feed a single linear SVM. DeepGaze [52] is a deeper CNN structure relative to the initial solutions of CNN for visual saliency, it uses 5-layers of CNN. Deepfix [53], a recently proposed popular solution, uses Fully-Connected Neural Networks (FCNN), unlike the majority of the deep learning solutions that use CNN. There are five convolution blocks whose initial weights are loaded from the VGG-16 [54] network. Zhao *et al.* [18] apply separate CNNs, one is for global, the other one is for local context information.

Goodfellow et al. [12] introduce a specific unsupervised deep learning approach called Generative Adversarial Nets (GAN). GAN structures embody two main networks: Generator and Discriminator. Within this approach, the generator is trained to confuse or fool the discriminator. On the other hand, the discriminator aims to correctly label inputs coming from the generator, whether they are real, i.e. from a provided train set or fake, i.e. yielded by the generator. There are several fields that GANs can be employed in both computer vision fields and non-vision fields like natural language processing [55]. It is used for data augmentation [56, 57], semantic segmentation [58], super-resolution [59, 60], image to image translation [15, 61], visual saliency [62, 63, 64] and so on. We focus on top-down attention, i.e. goal-oriented viewing, in chapter 4 and we use GAN approaches to train our collected data and get results.

2.3 Brief Overview of Related Datasets

There are several studies of eye fixation datasets, we will refer mostly used datasets. MIT300 dataset [65] contains eye fixation data of 39 viewers for freely-viewed 300 natural indoor and outdoor scenes. MIT1003 dataset [66] contains more images than MIT300 dataset. It contains eye fixation data of 15 viewers for freely-viewed 1003 natural indoor and outdoor scenes. CAT2000 [67] is a dataset of fixation data of 24 viewers for freely-viewed 4000 images from 20 different categories. SALICON [68] is a relatively new and extensive dataset that uses 20,000 images of MS COCO [69]. There are some other datasets which have free-viewing eye fixation data with a specific content like EMOd [70] which provides emotional contents observers to freely view, EyeCrowd [71] which has eye fixation data for crowded images, FiFA dataset [25] consists of images of people so that the study combines visual saliency with face detection. Besides these, there are search oriented datasets in which viewers were asked to search for a specific object [72, 73]. VIP dataset [74] has eye fixation data of 75 viewers for 150 images which are viewed freely as well as for anomaly detection tasks. As we can observe, most of these datasets provide eye fixation data for free-viewing, task-oriented saliency datasets are very few in number relative to the volume of the free-viewing datasets [75].

CHAPTER 3

FREE-VIEWING VISUAL SALIENCY

The human visual system (HVS) continuously utilizes the cognitive part of the visual attention, which enables us to quickly break down complex scenes by guiding the visual focus toward the conspicuous pieces of the scene. Such a procedure diminishes the intellectual weight while seeing the encompassing scene. Visual saliency system has been broadly studied in the cognitive science [1, 16] and it is commonly considered under free-viewing conditions. The bottom-up saliency can be computed by using low-level features like contrast, depth, orientation, color range, etc. and by using high-level features like semantics, surroundedness of the objects in visual stimuli, etc.

In this chapter, we elaborate on the studies we conducted on the bottom-up visual saliency methods. For this purpose, viewers of visual stimuli freely observe the visual stimuli for some time. We worked on state-of-the-art visual saliency methods to gain an understanding of their performance. Our work studies human gaze behavior on free-viewing for 2D desktop viewing as well as 3D VR viewing conditions. For the experiment, we assigned three scenes as a video sequence to the participants and asked them to watch these scenes freely. We collected their eye fixation data via eye tracker tools. To examine the bottom-up visual saliency methods in the literature. We analyzed the methods in detail by evaluating the metric results [76] that we obtained for our ground truth eye fixation data collected during the user experiment. Our preliminary work was published as a conference paper [77] and a journal article [78].

3.1 Evaluation of the bottom-up visual saliency methods

We assess the considered methods by getting results for the collected eye fixation data. We mainly consider below features and methods that use the features.

- **Super-Pixels:** A super-pixel is essentially a set of pixels with common characteristics. Super-pixels accelerate calculations, but forming super-pixels also yields a cost; the trade-off for the costs should be taken into consideration. In our work, the SLIC [79] method is used to generate the super-pixels.
- **Depth Map:** Two methods that we study prioritize the depth map by considering it as a separate channel. These methods adopt depth information as primary features and yield saliency maps by mainly using the depth map.
- **Boundary Connectivity:** Image boundary connectivity cue is used within two methods that are proposed in the same framework [36]. This is based on the assumption that the background part of a frame is connected with the borders of the frame.
- **Color Quantization:** The method [32] first quantizes an image by color and the spatial center and variances of the quantized colors are calculated. By doing that, basic features of the salient object, such as the position and the size, are estimated.
- **Surroundedness:** Surroundedness is used in the paper [80]. It is a function of the specific relation between the figure and the ground, which is invariant to various transformations.

We obtain results of the methods for our data and figure out how they are useful for both 2D viewing and 3D VR viewing conditions. We also examine different viewing behaviors between the 2D viewing condition and 3D VR viewing condition. In this section, we explain the methods that we have used.

Table 3.1: Hand-crafted features used by methods.

Features	Explanation	Used in
Super-pixels	Grouping pixels with common characteristics.	[44, 45]
Depth Map	Using the positioning of objects along the z-axis.	[44, 45]
Boundary Connectivity	The assumption of the background part of a frame is connected with the borders of the frame.	[36]
Color Quantization	Grouping by colors.	[32]
Surroundedness	A transformation invariant relation between the figure and the ground.	[80]

3.1.1 Boolean Map Saliency (BMS)

The surroundedness cue is mainly used for Boolean Map Saliency (BMS) study [81, 80]. In the BMS method, surroundedness cue is portrayed as the fenced-in area topological connection between the figure and the ground, which is very much characterized and invariant to different changes. According to its definition, regions connected to the image boundary are not surrounded with surroundedness value of 0 and vice versa with surroundedness value of 1. An illustration of the surroundedness cue is shown in figure 3.1. Boolean Map Theory of visual attention [37] is mainly adopted to compute Boolean Map Saliency frames. Boolean maps are produced by arbitrarily thresholding the features of the stimuli images. An attention map is processed for each Boolean map dependent on the surroundedness cue. The saliency maps are linearly joined to get a mean saliency map. The output saliency map is produced by applying some post-computations on the mean saliency map [80].

3.1.2 Fast, Accurate, and Size-Aware Salient Object Detection (FASA)

The primary advantage of this method, Fast, Accurate, and Size-Aware Salient Object Detection (FASA) [32], is its speed, as its name implies. The implementation of the method is started with color quantization. An input image is quantized by its colors by CIE L*a*b color space. We can say that this quantization simply diminishes color variety by grouping. This is performed for efficiency. The low-level features of the

Figure 3.1: The surroundedness cue is invariant to transformations.

salient objects like size, position are estimated with the computation of the spatial center and deviations of the grouped colors. These features are used for extracting saliency probabilities. The grouped color obtained by color quantization is also used for extracting global contrast scores. The final saliency map is the result of linear interpolation of the saliency probabilities with the global contrast scores.

3.1.3 Fine-Grained Saliency (FGS)

Fine-Grained Saliency (FGS) approach [82] adopts a visual saliency prediction approach based on center-surround differences with the main purpose of developing a viable human detection algorithm. The method works in three main stages: object segmentation, feature extraction, and object classification. The object segmentation is done by using depth continuity information in three steps: depth segmentation, analysis of connected components on each segmented layer and application of a set of filters in cascade to refine candidate spots using size and shape constraints. After the segmentation, feature extraction is performed based on visual saliency. The novelty of the method is the feature extraction part. For the feature extraction, utilized feature components are based on a biologically inspired attention system [17, 83], at input image resolution by using an integral image as defined in [84]. Finally, classification is carried out using a feed-forward neural network trained with back-propagation.

3.1.4 Minimum Barrier Salient Object Detection (MB, MB+)

Minimum Barrier Salient Object Detection study [36] proposes two visual saliency approaches, MB and MB+. Both approaches adopt the image boundary connectivity cue. The image boundary connectivity cue is built on the assumption that the background portion of a frame is connected to the frame's borders. Minimum barrier distance (MBD) maps are calculated by approximating distance transform algorithm to compute image boundary connectivity of each pixel in an image. The MBD maps are generated for each color channel and the MBD maps of different color channels are averaged into a single MBD map. Then, the output MB saliency map is obtained through a few post-processing steps on the averaged MBD map to efficiently optimize the segmentation of salient objects. Apart from these steps, an appearance-based backgroundness cue is for the generation of MB+ saliency maps. This background cue implies the background of a frame is not only connected but also similar to the boundary regions of the image.

3.1.5 Anisotropic Center-Surround Difference (ACSD)

This approach [44] gives priority to depth knowledge and spatial information. Using an optical flow method, the depth map of the image is generated. The center-surround anisotropic difference (ACSD) is defined as a measure of depth contrast at the center of each super-pixel. The super-pixels are generated using the simple linear iterative clustering (SLIC) algorithm [79]. An anisotropic scan is carried out along multiple scanlines for ACSD computation. In each scanline, the super-pixel with the minimum average depth, i.e., the farthest one, is assumed as background and the depth difference between the center and the background gives ACSD along this scanline. ACSD of a super-pixel is calculated by summing ACSD values of 8 scanlines, each crossing through the centroid of one of the eight immediate neighbors of the super-pixel under consideration. After scaling to $[0, 255]$ range, the pixel-wise saliency assignment is performed based on the centroid values. Next, a linear weighting is added to the far half of the pixels to ensure that regions closer to the viewer appear more conspicuous. And finally, a 2D Gaussian centered over the image is applied due to the prior that objects at the center tend to be found more salient [85, 86].

3.1.6 Local Background Enclosure for RGB-D Salient Object Detection (LBE)

Weighting the depth feature apart from other features may result in false-positive predictions for salient regions in an image if the range of the depth values of the image background is wide. Local Background Enclosure for RGB-D Salient Object Detection (LBE) proposes a different approach for the usage of depth feature [45]. It introduces the local background enclosure (LBE) feature, which computes the volume of object boundaries placed on the foreground. Before LBE features are extracted, super-pixel segmentation is calculated for a given RGB-D image. LBE features for the calculated super-pixels are extracted. Then, the depth and spatial information are used and background cues are used. Lastly, Grabcut segmentation [87] is applied to the result of the previous steps and that gives the final saliency map of the algorithm.

3.2 User study

3.2.1 Participants

We performed our experiments with 13 female and 17 male participants whose mean age is 27 ± 4.07 with normal or corrected-to-normal sight. All the participants were attended to our experiment voluntarily without having any monetary or any other kind of award. The participants were informed about the experiment before starting and they signed a consent form. They were also told that they could leave the experiment any time they need and they are not forced to finish the experiment if they do not want. They were informed that their names and their gaze data collected during the experiment to be anonymous. The participants attended our experiment for both 2D viewing condition and 3D VR viewing condition. The participants were also asked about their level of experience with VR. They signed the level on a 5-point Likert scale in which 0 stands for "no experience at all" whereas four stands for "highly experienced". The mean scale of indicated experience was 1.09 ± 0.9 . 14 of the 30 participants had no prior VR experience. The participants were either an engineering background or social science degree or freshman student with no technical background. Visual acuities of all the participants were tested before attending the experiment.

3.2.2 Experiment setup

Eye fixations of the participants were collected for both 2D viewing condition and 3D VR viewing condition for the same scenes/contents. For 2D viewing condition, Tobii Alienware R4 (Intel i7 7700 HQ 2.8 GHz, Nvidia GeForce GTX 1070, 17-inch screen) containing Tobii Aware eye tracker with 3840 x 2160 pixels screen is used. The integrated eye tracker provides gaze points for 2D viewing condition, it has a high-resolution sensor for eye-tracking that includes NIR (near-infrared) illuminators. The GPU of the laptop is Nvidia GeForce GTX 1070 and the processor is four-core Intel i7 7700 HQ, 2.8 GHz. The participants viewed the contents with a 60 cm distance to the laptop monitor. For 3D viewing condition, the participants equipped the HTC Vive VR system with an HMD containing the Tobii Pro eye tracker. During the user study, the headset was connected to a desktop computer with an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-6700 CPU, 16 GB RAM, and an Nvidia GeForce GTX 1050 Ti. The integrated eye tracker provides gaze points for 3D viewing condition. The eye tracker works at 120 Hz frequency with an estimated accuracy of 0.5°. The trackable field of view is 110°. The eye tracker is integrated with cameras that are hidden behind the lenses. There are ten infrared illuminators and one eye-tracking sensor per eye.

Figure 3.2: HMD with an integrated eye tracker for 3D VR viewing condition.
<https://vr.tobii.com/>

3.2.3 Scenes

Unity game & simulation engine [9] is used for content generation to be shown during the experiment and eye fixation data of the participants are collected while they are viewing the generated content. Three different contents are created via the game

Figure 3.3: Sample frames from the scenes.

engine, see figure 3.3. We refer to the contents as scenes. The scenes are shown to the participants in the same sequence for both viewing conditions. An outdoor environment is chosen for the first scene (hereinafter, the outdoor scene), an abstract content is used for the second scene (hereinafter, the abstract scene) and a room as an indoor setting is designed for the third scene (hereinafter, the indoor scene). Durations of the scene are 38 seconds, 30 seconds, and 28 seconds, respectively. The participants freely viewed these scenes without any interaction. These scenes flow after calibration and automatically stop when each of them is finished. Between the scenes, a gray display was shown for 10 seconds so that the participants take a break and be ready for the next scene.

3.2.4 Experimental procedure

Before starting the experiment, the participants are briefed about the setting and the procedure of the experiment without informing about the main purpose of the experiment. We clearly stated that collected data would be used anonymously for academic purposes. After giving the necessary information, we asked participants to sign a con-

sent form. We initialize the experimental procedure with the sight tests. The participants were tested for Monoyer chart to check visual acuity, the Ishihara test to check the color vision, and random-dot stereogram test to check the stereo acuity and depth perception. At the beginning of the viewing, calibration processes of the eye trackers are conducted. Eye trackers of both viewing conditions have similar calibration processes. Random circles appear in the scene and the participants follow the circles and the eye-trackers calibrate themselves by using circles known position, orientation and fixation data obtained from the participants [88]. If the calibration is successful, the experiment starts by itself. During the experiment, the participants viewed the prepared scenes freely. The contents of the scenes stream as a video sequence with pre-defined wandering paths. As the camera goes along the pre-defined paths, the participants observe the scene with free-viewing. When a scene is done, it stops automatically and calibration is performed for the next scene after the participants take a 5-minute break. When three scenes are finished, the experiment ends.

3.3 Results

Within this study, our goal is to examine different saliency methods that mainly use different features for bottom-up saliency. We evaluated the performance of the methods for our content by using different saliency metrics. Since we have an opportunity to collect data for free-viewing of both 2D and 3D VR viewing conditions, we also compare the viewing behavior for different viewing conditions.

3.3.1 Viewing behaviour for different viewing conditions

Ground truth eye fixation density maps show that if the range of the depth values of a stimuli image is wide or there are visible, salient objects in a far distance, the distinction between viewing behavior for 2D and 3D viewing conditions is considerably different. Eye fixation points are placed further points if there are conspicuous parts on the further points for 2D viewing condition, while they are placed on closer points for 3D viewing condition. A similar viewing behavior for 2D and 3D viewing condition appears when the range of the depth value of the images is small. That is,

Figure 3.4: The heat maps and the fixation density maps of 2D and 3D viewing behaviours which are the least similar for outdoor (first row), abstract (second row) and indoor (third row) scenes.

the output of the 3D viewing condition matches the 2D viewing condition, such that the eye fixations mostly cluster on points closer to the camera. 2D viewing behavior becomes similar for these frames that have a small range of depth values. The frames that have the least and the most similar viewing behavior between 2D and 3D viewing conditions are shown in figures 3.4 and 3.5. In these figures, the first two columns are the heat maps and the fixation density maps of the ground truth of the given image in 2D viewing condition and the last two are the heat maps and the fixation density maps of the ground truth of the given image in 3D viewing condition.

3.3.2 Evaluation of the saliency methods

Average scores of MIT Saliency Benchmark metrics are given in table 3.2 and the scores are visualized in figure 3.6. AUC-Borji [89], AUC-Judd [66], Similarity (SIM) -histogram intersection-, Pearson’s linear coefficient (CC) and normalized scanpath saliency (NSS) metrics are the similarity metrics whereas Kullback-Leibler divergence (KL) is the dissimilarity metric [76], see appendix for details. For similarity metrics, higher scores imply better results, for dissimilarity metrics the opposite is

Figure 3.5: The heat maps and the fixation density maps of 2D and 3D viewing behaviours which are the most similar for outdoor (first row), abstract (second row) and indoor (third row) scenes.

true. Overall scores show that BMS outperforms other methods in terms of Similarity, KL, CC, and NSS metric scores for 2D viewing condition, while MB and MB+ outperform other methods by all the metrics except for CC metric. We can also observe the same for the outdoor scene and for the indoor scene except for the NSS metric. For the abstract scene mostly MB and MB+ methods yield the best scores. MB+ gives the best scores for AUC-Borji and KL metrics whereas MB outperforms other methods for Similarity, CC, and NSS metrics. We notice that the performance of the methods by the metric scores is similar for the outdoor scene and the abstract scene with 2D and 3D VR viewing conditions. For the indoor scene, BMS performs the best for Similarity and KL metrics under 2D viewing condition, while MB and MB+ perform best for these metrics, respectively, under 3D VR viewing condition. When we examine metric results for overall scenes, we see that MB+ scores the best of AUC-Borji metric for both 2D and 3D VR viewing conditions and KL metric for 3D VR viewing condition; MB gives the best scores of AUC-Judd for both viewing conditions and Similarity and NSS for 3D VR viewing condition; BMS results in the best metric scores of CC for both viewing conditions and Similarity, KL, NSS for 2D viewing conditions. When we check all the metric scores, we can say that BMS is the

best method for 2D viewing condition whereas MB and MB+ are the best methods for 3D VR viewing conditions.

Table 3.2: Average scores for (a) 2D and (b) 3D viewing conditions. Bold scores are best for that column. Shown scores are truncated to two decimal places to illustrate.

(a)	Overall						Outdoor Scene					
	AUC - Borji	AUC - Judd	Similarity	KL	CC	NSS	AUC - Borji	AUC - Judd	Similarity	KL	CC	NSS
BMS	0.53	0.75	0.36	1.13	0.39	0.58	0.53	0.67	0.28	1.21	0.32	0.48
FASA	0.53	0.58	0.24	2.18	0.11	0.16	0.53	0.61	0.20	2.09	0.08	0.18
FG	0.50	0.59	0.24	2.02	0.08	0.14	0.50	0.48	0.17	2.51	-0.04	-0.07
MB	0.52	0.77	0.35	1.74	0.31	0.53	0.50	0.68	0.24	1.90	0.11	0.26
MB+	0.54	0.67	0.29	1.22	0.23	0.38	0.50	0.52	0.20	1.55	0.01	0.00
ACSD	0.52	0.50	0.21	5.69	0.03	0.10	0.54	0.56	0.21	6.49	0.03	0.19
LBE	0.51	0.47	0.20	3.19	-0.01	-0.02	0.48	0.53	0.18	3.03	-0.05	-0.03

(b)	Overall						Outdoor Scene					
	AUC - Borji	AUC - Judd	Similarity	KL	CC	NSS	AUC - Borji	AUC - Judd	Similarity	KL	CC	NSS
BMS	0.52	0.74	0.39	1.07	0.43	0.45	0.52	0.68	0.31	1.04	0.4	0.46
FASA	0.51	0.54	0.26	2.22	0.11	0.08	0.53	0.60	0.22	2.05	0.09	0.16
FG	0.51	0.62	0.27	1.75	0.11	0.18	0.51	0.52	0.19	2.27	-0.02	0.06
MB	0.51	0.78	0.39	1.68	0.36	0.45	0.50	0.73	0.27	1.60	0.16	0.36
MB+	0.54	0.66	0.32	1.06	0.28	0.31	0.51	0.56	0.22	1.31	0.05	0.11
ACSD	0.53	0.51	0.22	5.38	0.02	0.12	0.55	0.57	0.20	6.84	-0.02	0.21
LBE	0.51	0.48	0.21	2.88	-0.03	0.00	0.50	0.59	0.18	2.97	-0.10	0.05

(a)	Abstract Scene						Indoor Scene					
	AUC - Borji	AUC - Judd	Similarity	KL	CC	NSS	AUC - Borji	AUC - Judd	Similarity	KL	CC	NSS
BMS	0.54	0.84	0.43	1.13	0.49	0.80	0.51	0.74	0.37	1.06	0.35	0.47
FASA	0.52	0.50	0.23	2.33	0.14	0.10	0.53	0.62	0.28	2.11	0.11	0.22
FG	0.52	0.76	0.32	1.62	0.27	0.50	0.49	0.52	0.23	1.93	0.01	-0.02
MB	0.54	0.84	0.44	2.11	0.52	0.82	0.51	0.78	0.36	1.21	0.29	0.5
MB+	0.6	0.78	0.36	1.04	0.47	0.78	0.54	0.69	0.31	1.06	0.23	0.37
ACSD	0.51	0.42	0.17	6.26	-0.04	-0.07	0.52	0.51	0.26	4.31	0.12	0.16
LBE	0.52	0.44	0.19	3.56	-0.03	-0.05	0.52	0.43	0.24	2.97	0.06	0.03

(b)	Abstract Scene						Indoor Scene					
	AUC - Borji	AUC - Judd	Similarity	KL	CC	NSS	AUC - Borji	AUC - Judd	Similarity	KL	CC	NSS
BMS	0.53	0.83	0.45	1.22	0.46	0.59	0.51	0.70	0.41	0.96	0.43	0.29
FASA	0.51	0.48	0.26	2.09	0.15	0.02	0.50	0.54	0.30	2.52	0.09	0.05
FG	0.52	0.78	0.36	1.34	0.30	0.44	0.50	0.56	0.27	1.63	0.06	0.04
MB	0.53	0.83	0.48	2.33	0.53	0.6	0.51	0.79	0.43	1.09	0.40	0.4
MB+	0.57	0.75	0.38	0.96	0.48	0.56	0.53	0.67	0.36	0.91	0.30	0.27
ACSD	0.52	0.47	0.20	5.26	-0.02	0.05	0.52	0.50	0.26	4.04	0.11	0.11
LBE	0.51	0.44	0.20	2.89	-0.04	-0.05	0.51	0.43	0.24	2.79	0.04	0.00

Figure 3.6: Visualization of table 3.2. For similarity metrics, higher scores imply better results, for dissimilarity metrics the opposite is true.

3.4 Conclusion

When we analyze the average scores for overall scenes and each scene separately, see table 3.2; based on these, we can say that BMS, MB, and MB+ performs best. MB and MB+ commonly utilize the boundary connectivity cue and BMS primarily adopts the surroundedness cue. Both of these cues use the relationship of the object and its background with different approaches. We can conclude that this relationship is crucial for saliency prediction under both 2D and 3D VR viewing conditions. The overall metric scores, except for NSS, show that these methods perform slightly better for 3D VR viewing condition. Previous studies [10, 11] show that depth feature is crucial for visual attention, but we conclude that approaches like ACSD and LBE that focus on the depth feature heavily, may not yield good result.

CHAPTER 4

TASK-ORIENTED VISUAL SALIENCY

We studied on free-viewing saliency methods with hand-crafted features, as we elaborate in chapter 3. We gain an understanding of the concept of visual saliency and some of the hand-crafted features. We determine to continue our study by using deep learning approaches since they perform better than hand-crafted features [90]. We handle not only free-viewing visual saliency but also task-oriented visual saliency in this chapter because we aim at extending our study by including the task-oriented attention type. We would like to extend our scope in this direction mostly because semantics, such as where people are placed in the frame, what text warns about, in the visual frame is important and focusing on attention with semantics is a good direction for visual saliency methods [91, 92]. Task-oriented attention is about semantics and requires different brain activities, so it is performed with more effort than free-viewing [93]. Because free-viewing is mostly handled with low-level features that need not much of cognitive complexity, whereas task-oriented attention requires high level-features accompanied by cognitive complexity [94, 95]. Most of the studies in computer vision mainly focus on bottom-up saliency, even though task-oriented, i.e. top-down, attention has more usage in daily life [96] for locating (searching for milk), directing (grabbing an item from the shelf), guiding (lid on a kettle) and checking (water bottle while filling) [97]. It is also crucial for practices such as video game playing [98, 99] or traffic driving environments [100]. By considering the importance of this field, we also conducted a study on task-oriented visual saliency in addition to the free-viewing. To handle more than one attention type, we propose a single network approach. We predict that a single network approach can also be used for different viewing conditions as long as data for training is in hand. We adopt different GAN approaches to get results for collected data for three task-based attention and

free-viewing. The first approach that we consider is an image-to-image translation approach [15] in which a mapping between pairs of images is formed by utilizing a proper, learned loss function by conditional GAN. With that setting, the condition is the input image and its corresponding pair is generated as output. Secondly, we focused on a different GAN approach [64] that uses two different generators for local and global features and two different discriminators as fine-scale and coarse-scale.

Initially, we prepared an experiment setting with 492 still images from existing datasets. Half of the images were chosen from EMotional Attention Dataset (EMOd) dataset [70] and the other half of the images were chosen from Saliency in Crowd (Eye-Crowd) [71] dataset. We eliminate images that awake strong and edge emotions in viewers so that their focuses are not manipulated by the strong emotions and block them from performing the assigned task while they are viewing the image. Since Eye-Crowd [71] study explores visual attention for a wide range of crowds, their dataset may include images that have an excessive number of people in them. We include the images that contain less than 15 people because what we needed is to provide content for participants to view, not visual attention in crowd analysis. We specified three tasks to consider while viewing the still images, inspired by Yarbus’s study [101]. Our experiment setting is designed as between-subjects; in total, we have four groups of participants, three of which perform three assigned tasks on the same 492 still images, whereas one group is asked to free-view the same 492 still images.

4.1 Our Experiment

4.1.1 Participants

There are 8 participants for each task-based viewing and the free-viewing; in sum, 32 participants joined our experiment. We have conducted the experiment with the 32 participants whose mean age is $25,13 \pm 3,86$ and 13 of them are female, 19 of them are male with normal or corrected-to-normal visual acuity. All the participants were attended to our experiment voluntarily without having any monetary or any other kind of award. The participants were informed about the experiment before starting and they signed a consent form. They were also told that they could leave the experiment

any time they need and they are not forced to finish the experiment if they do not want. They were informed that they and their gaze data would be anonymous and their gaze data collected, during the experiment, by SMI eye tracker will be used for our study.

4.1.2 Experimental details

We used the SMI eye tracker model of SMI RED-60 Hz with a monitor connected to a DELL laptop to collect gaze data of the participants. The participant viewed still images on 22" monitor and the eye tracker placed at the bottom of the monitor 4.1 collected fixation data of the participants while they were viewing. There were 8 participants for each task-based viewing and the free-viewing; in sum, 32 participants joined our experiment. We have conducted the experiment with the 32 participants whose mean age is $25,13 \pm 3,86$ and 13 of them are female, 19 of them are male with normal or corrected-to-normal visual acuity. All the participants were attended to our experiment voluntarily without having any monetary or any other kind of award. The participants were informed about the experiment before starting and they signed a consent form. They were also told that they could leave the experiment any time they need and they are not forced to finish the experiment if they do not want. They were informed that their names and their gaze data would be anonymous. During their participation, gaze data were collected by an eye tracker, which we used for our study. After they were informed, they were tested for Monoyer chart to check visual acuity, the Ishihara test to check the color vision before the data collection starts. In total, 492 images were shown to each participant as five sets in which the sets had approximately the same number of images. Each image was shown for 4 seconds. After the shown duration was ended, the next image was loaded without any interaction. Each set was started after a successful 5-point calibration and ended automatically. The participants gave a 5-minute break between the sets. Calibrations were performed with the help of the experiment instructor. After each calibration was all set, the participant was by her/his own to view the stimuli freely or with an assigned task. During a participant viewed given images, eye-tracking software SMI IViewX on the DELL laptop was run and collect data. After all the data collecting is done, fixation density maps are obtained via SMI BEGAZE software.

Figure 4.1: Viewing monitor with SMI eye tracker.
<https://imotions.com/hardware/smi-red/>

4.2 Analysis of collected data

We collected the eye fixation data of participants for three different tasks and free-viewing. The participants were asked to answer or complete these tasks while they are viewing the visual stimuli, which are 492 still images. This provided shifting attention to different points between the tasks for the participants. Hereinafter, we also count free-viewing condition as a separate task (i.e. no task condition) and we will point out that we used four tasks.

- For task 1, we asked the participants to count people in the frame, if any, as they can, and come up with a number, the number does not necessarily have to be very exact, the amount that they could count.
- For task 2, we asked the participants to find an answer for emotion in the frame and people's feelings in the frame. Before the experiment, some examples are given as 'sad', 'happy', 'angry', etc. and they were also free to choose different words for the emotions as they can think of during viewing.
- For task 3, the participants were asked to define the occasion in the frame, if any, or what person/people in the frame is/are doing.
- Task 4 is free-viewing in which the participants were not asked for any task

they were told that viewing shown images, freely.

We expect corresponding eye fixation maps to be slightly distinct as we aim to propose the same GAN network for all the tasks. If gaze behavior for different tasks were very similar, we wouldn't show the performance of a single GAN network. We would not show the network performs well for different eye fixation distributions. We also did not expect uncorrelated maps since the shown content is the same even though the tasks are different. In order to examine similarities of the fixation maps for different tasks, we used distribution-based metrics. We apply similarity metrics of Pearson's Correlation Coefficient (CC) and histogram intersection (SIM) and a dissimilarity metric of Kullback-Leibler divergence (KL). In contrast with the comparison between fixation density maps and saliency maps, we expect these metrics yield results implying the similarity between measured maps is not high. To clarify, similarity or dissimilarity metrics are mostly used for the comparison between fixation density maps, i.e. ground truths, and generated saliency maps. The purpose of the comparison is measuring the success of the generated saliency maps, the success is proportional to the similarity [102]. Two maps, the saliency map and ground truths, are compared and high similarity is expected for good performance of the saliency maps. At this phase of our study, we used these metrics to make sure that ground truths for different tasks are not very similar as well as they are not very dissimilar. We use them not for the comparison of saliency maps and ground truths, instead, we use them to check the similarity of gaze behaviors between ground truths of different tasks. We want the ground truths between tasks not to be very similar so that collecting gaze data for different tasks and performance of the single network covers these different tasks to make sense. Based on these scores, if these ground truths of each stimulus for different tasks were very similar, using different tasks would not be an important component. However, our study is mostly about proposing a solution for different tasks, thus, we want ground truths of different tasks to be slightly distinct. Also, it is not realistic to expect the ground truths to be very distinct and uncorrelated since the content is the same for different tasks. Briefly, we expect differences between different task conditions so that our study has a claim and we also predict that ground truths of different tasks not to be entirely different because the contents are the same for different tasks. Based on the average results of SIM, CC, and KL

metrics, for all stimuli of 492 still images, we observe that the highest dissimilarities are obtained between task 1 and task 4. This makes sense because task 1 is counting people in the frame which requires detailed viewing of the participants whereas task 4 is free-viewing which generally requires a glimpse of the scene by the participants. We also detect that the highest similarities are obtained between task 2 and task 3 for SIM and CC metrics, between task 1 and task 2 for KL metric. Overall, it can be seen in table 4.1 that the scores are close to each other for each metric and imply that fixations for different tasks are not similar as well as they are not uncorrelated, either. In figure 4.2 and figure 4.3 stimuli and related heat maps by tasks are displayed whose metric scores are averaged by four tasks. figure 4.2 shows least similar fixation map’s original image and heat maps by each metric score and figure 4.3 shows most similars.

Table 4.1: Fixation density map similarities by tasks. For CC and SIM higher scores, for KL lower scores mean more similar.

<i>CC</i>	<i>task1</i>	<i>task2</i>	<i>task3</i>	<i>task4</i>	<i>SIM</i>	<i>task1</i>	<i>task2</i>	<i>task3</i>	<i>task4</i>	<i>KL</i>	<i>task1</i>	<i>task2</i>	<i>task3</i>	<i>task4</i>
<i>task1</i>		0.492	0.467	0.460	<i>task1</i>		0.426	0.410	0.408	<i>task1</i>		5.309	6.633	6.715
<i>task2</i>	0.492		0.604	0.595	<i>task2</i>	0.426		0.489	0.482	<i>task2</i>	5.309		5.445	5.689
<i>task3</i>	0.467	0.604		0.563	<i>task3</i>	0.410	0.489		0.461	<i>task3</i>	6.633	5.445		5.851
<i>task4</i>	0.460	0.595	0.563		<i>task4</i>	0.408	0.482	0.461		<i>task4</i>	6.715	5.689	5.851	

Figure 4.2: Example images which have most dissimilarity between tasks

4.3 Approach

Image-to-image networks can be used for visual saliency [103]. We adopted a conditional GAN (cGAN) based image-to-image translation approach [15] (hereinafter referred to as *pix2pix*) and another cGAN approach to estimate visual saliency [64]

Figure 4.3: Example images which have most similarity between tasks

(hereinafter referred to as *sal-cfs-gan*). *Sal-cfs-gan* proposes two different versions, the first one utilizes local and global modified U-Nets without using Center-Surround-Connections, which is referred to as the baseline (hereinafter referred to as *local*) and the second one utilizes local and global modified U-Nets equipped with cross-scale Center-Surround-Connections (hereinafter referred to as *csc*). Both of these studies get pairs of images as stimuli and their corresponding fixation density maps as ground truth and use the pairs for the training of a cGAN architecture. We collected eye fixation data of 492 images for each task. We use the data to train adopted studies, as it is, we will refer to it as *separate training*. Also, we developed an approach in which we train all the data, collected for each task and we will refer to it as *single training*. Our main purpose is to use a single network that can handle different tasks at one training as separate training does.

4.3.1 Separate Training

We use the adopted pix2pix and *sal-cfs-gan* studies as they are. We perform a total of four separate training for four defined tasks. We have 492 images that have corresponding fixation density maps for each task separately. To clarify, we have 492 stimuli RGB images common between the tasks, whereas their ground truth fixation density maps are varied by the tasks. Thus, we have $492 \times 4 = 1968$ fixation density maps to be used as ground truths, so we have 1968 image-map pairs which are trained and tested four times, one training per one task, with $1968/4 = 492$ image-map pairs. Briefly, we perform training separately for each task. We use 400 of the pairs for training, 46 of the pairs for validation during training, and 46 of the pairs are used as unseen examples for testing. An illustration of the training approach is shown in

figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4: Training structure, this is applied for each task, separately.

4.3.2 Single Training

For single training, we use the same adopted studies. However, in this approach, we perform single training by using all the image-map pairs in addition to task labels. The purpose of this is to come up with a solution that embraces a saliency map estimation for different conditions, i.e. tasks, at once. 1600 of the pairs are used for training, 184 of the pairs are used for validation during training and the remaining 184 of the pairs are used as unseen examples for testing. An illustration of the single training approach is shown in figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5: Training structure is performed once.

4.4 Results

We train with our collected data and evaluate the results for both pix2pix and sal-cfs-gan approaches with default implementations and with our single network approach. What we try to achieve is to show a single network approach for different gaze conditions by getting plausible results for the single network. We evaluate the results by ROC curves, similarity metrics of Pearson's linear coefficient, histogram intersection (SIM), and dissimilarity metric of Kullback-Leibler divergence (KL), see appendix for details. The reason for us to choose these metrics is that they are more convenient

for comparing saliency maps and ground truth fixation density maps than the other metrics, the other metrics are better for discrete maps rather than continuous maps as we have [102]. We evaluate 2 cases for pix2pix approach: single training and separate training. We assess 4 cases for sal-cfs-gan approach: single training and separate training for local and single training and separate training for csc. Figure 4.6 shows ROC curves for single and separate training for the pix2pix approach. Results of CC, SIM, and KL metrics for both the single and the separate training are displayed in table 4.2.

Figure 4.6: Roc curves for single and separate training for the pix2pix approach.

Table 4.2: Left table shows scores of single network for pix2pix study, right table stands for default case, separate networks. Bold scores are the best for metric column.

	<i>CC</i>	<i>SIM</i>	<i>KL</i>
<i>task 1</i>	0.593	0.613	4.241
<i>task 2</i>	0.643	0.623	3.089
<i>task 3</i>	0.631	0.589	3.673
<i>task 4</i>	0.582	0.591	3.981

	<i>CC</i>	<i>SIM</i>	<i>KL</i>
<i>task 1</i>	0.558	0.513	4.587
<i>task 2</i>	0.629	0.614	3.512
<i>task 3</i>	0.546	0.499	4.469
<i>task 4</i>	0.621	0.535	4.072

Figure 4.7 shows ROC curves for single and separate training of the sal-cfs-gan local approach. Results of CC, SIM, and KL metrics for both the single and the separate training are displayed in table 4.3.

Figure 4.7: Roc curves for single and separate training for the sal-cfs-gan local approach.

Table 4.3: The left table shows scores of single network for local version of sal-cfs-gan study, the right table stands for separate training of the same version. Bold scores are the best for the metric column.

	<i>CC</i>	<i>SIM</i>	<i>KL</i>
<i>task 1</i>	0.705	0.707	2.611
<i>task 2</i>	0.662	0.689	2.902
<i>task 3</i>	0.645	0.648	3.321
<i>task 4</i>	0.653	0.640	3.635

	<i>CC</i>	<i>SIM</i>	<i>KL</i>
<i>task 1</i>	0.664	0.674	2.820
<i>task 2</i>	0.629	0.656	3.134
<i>task 3</i>	0.614	0.617	3.585
<i>task 4</i>	0.622	0.610	3.921

Figure 4.8 shows ROC curves for single and separate training of the sal-cfs-gan csc approach. Results of CC, SIM, and KL metrics for both the single and the separate training are displayed in table 4.4.

Figure 4.8: Roc curves for single and separate training for the sal-cfs-gan csc approach.

Table 4.4: The left table shows scores of single network for csc version of the sal-cfs-gan study, the right table stands for separate training of the same version. Bold scores are the best for the metric column.

	<i>CC</i>	<i>SIM</i>	<i>KL</i>
<i>task 1</i>	0.716	0.717	2.491
<i>task 2</i>	0.729	0.703	2.976
<i>task 3</i>	0.634	0.643	3.689
<i>task 4</i>	0.631	0.624	3.727

	<i>CC</i>	<i>SIM</i>	<i>KL</i>
<i>task 1</i>	0.674	0.683	2.694
<i>task 2</i>	0.693	0.670	3.215
<i>task 3</i>	0.603	0.613	3.980
<i>task 4</i>	0.600	0.595	4.020

Figure 4.9: Roc curves for all.

4.5 Conclusion

When we evaluate and compare all the results for all of the 6 cases we draw some conclusions. By checking overall roc curves in Figure 4.9 and CC, SIM, KL metrics in Figure 4.10, we can say that all the approaches perform better on task 1 and task 2

than task 3 and task 4. We also infer that sal-cfs-gan [64] for all of its 4 cases achieve better saliency estimations than pix2pix [15], especially for task 1 and task 2. It is observed that local and csc show similar performance in terms of saliency prediction. They may outperform the other for different tasks, overall, we can say that their scores are similar, though. We can also infer that the single training does not outperform the separate training and vice versa. Note that, we did not necessarily mean to outperform the separate training with the proposed single training approach, yet. What we try to achieve is to recommend and show a single network that embraces saliency estimation for different viewing conditions. An improved single approach that performs better than separate training for different viewing conditions can be a future direction.

(a) Visualization of CC metric, higher is for better results.

(b) Visualization of SIM metric, higher is for better results.

(c) Visualization of KL metric, lower is for better results.

Figure 4.10: Visualization of CC, SIM and KL metrics for all cases.

	Heatmap	Ground truth fixation density map	Result of single training	Result of separate training
Task 1				
Task 2				
Task 3				
Task 4				

Figure 4.11: A sample from ground truths and corresponding stimuli's saliency map results for pix2pix single and separate approaches.

	Heatmap	Ground truth fixation density map	Result of single training	Result of separate training
Task 1				
Task 2				
Task 3				
Task 4				

Figure 4.12: A sample from ground truths and corresponding stimuli's saliency map results for sal-cfs-gan local single and separate approaches.

		Heatmap	Ground truth fixation density map	Result of single training	Result of separate training
Task 1					
Task 2					
Task 3					
Task 4					

Figure 4.13: A sample from ground truths and corresponding stimuli's saliency map results for sal-cfs-gan csc single and separate approaches.

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION

5.1 Conclusion and Discussion

Our goal in this thesis was to study the visual saliency methods and the visual saliency term and propose a broad viewpoint for visual saliency solutions that embrace different visual attention types described in chapter 1. We initialize our work by focusing on traditional visual saliency approaches for bottom-up visual attention, free-viewing. Within this study, we cover 3D VR viewing conditions as well as 2D desktop viewing conditions. We conclude that one of the primary saliency features, especially for 3D VR viewing condition, do not work well when it is a weighted feature. We observe that even though the visual saliency methods we consider are novel and successful methods, it may not work well all the time and for all viewing conditions. This leads us to prefer deep learning methods for our second study. For the second study, we study top-down visual attention, i.e. goal-oriented viewing. We train GAN approaches [15, 64] for our stimuli images and their corresponding ground truths of eye-fixation density maps collected for four different viewing goals (one of them is free-viewing). We use the approaches as they are, separately for each viewing goals and get results. We propose to use a single of these networks with several discriminators, one for each goal and get results for the data of different viewing goals from the single networks. Thus, we train 400 train samples, 46 validation samples for each training when train separately each task and 1600 train samples, 184 validation samples for the single network that serves training of four different viewing goals. We predict that the latter version of the training performs slightly better because it has more training samples. Even though the number of samples that feed each discriminator is the same as the separate training, we expect that low-level features can be

learned better with overall more data. However, obtained results in section 4.4 show that the results of the separate and the single training by the evaluation metrics are pretty much similar. There are some cases each of them performs better than the other, but we cannot observe that the single version distinguishably outperforms the separate training. We think that the underlying reason for this is the lack of data. Our determination to prefer GAN approaches rather than other deep learning methods is GAN can achieve good results with the lack of data [13, 14, 15]. The major challenge that we encounter was data collection. Tailored data serving our studies cannot be found in the literature, so we needed to collect our data, which takes considerable time of the participants, which makes the data collection challenging and significant factor. In brief, we believe that our results of single training are not unsuccessful, but it does not surpass the results of separate training and it can be improved.

5.2 Future Work

Within this thesis, we study the visual saliency for different viewing conditions and for the different attention types. We contributed with collected eye-fixation data of the participants who attend our use studies. We provide an approach for an integrative solution for different goals of the viewers. This idea can be improved and used for different viewing conditions as well as different viewing goals or maybe mixed of different attention types and viewing conditions. This can be considered for integrating 2D and 3D viewing conditions into a single structure. Different deep learning approaches can be employed and the improvements can be made by comparing the results of the different deep learning approaches and GAN. Certainly, much of the data is always welcomed, provided more data always improve what is offered.

5.3 Related Publications

D. Albayrak, M.B. Askin, T.K. Capin, and U. Celikcan, “Visual Saliency Prediction in Dynamic Virtual Reality Environments Experienced with Head-mounted Displays: An Exploratory Study”, in 2019 International Conference on Cyberworlds (CW), pp. 61–68, IEEE, 2019.

U. Celikcan, M.B. Askin, D. Albayrak, and T.K. Capin, “Deep Into Visual Saliency for Immersive VR Environments Rendered in Real-time”, Computers & Graphics, 2020.

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APPENDIX

VISUAL SALIENCY EVALUATION METRICS

AUC-Borji

This computes the area under the ROC curve in which a higher area means a more accurate saliency map. While calculating the corresponding curve, it uses a uniform random sample of map pixels as negatives and labels false positives as any saliency map values above the threshold of these pixels. The range of this metric is [0, 1].

AUC-Judd

Similar to AUC-Borji, this metric also considers the ratio of true positives and false positives. Unlike AUC-Borji, the threshold values are generated from the saliency map's values rather than uniform random sampling. The range of this metric is [0, 1].

Kullback-Leibler Divergence (KL)

It measures dissimilarities between two maps. It measures lost information on saliency map SM when it is compared to fixation density map FM. Its range is $[0, \infty]$, minimum scores imply better saliency maps.

$$KL(SM, FM) = \sum_i^n FM_i * \log\left(\frac{FM_i}{SM_i + \epsilon} + \epsilon\right)$$

where ϵ is small constant to handle zero division.

Normalized Scanpath Saliency (NSS)

To obtain NSS score, normalization is applied to the saliency map. By considering fixation points and normalized values a correspondence is measured. It has a range of $[-\infty, \infty]$ where negative values show anti-correspondence, the positive values show correspondence such that higher values mean better saliency maps.

$$NSS(SM, FM) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i^n SM'_i * FM_i \quad \text{where}$$

$$SM' = \frac{SM - \mu(SM)}{\sigma(SM)}$$

Pearson's Correlation Coefficient (CC)

This metric shows a statistical correlation between two different distributions. For saliency evaluation, it gives a linear correlation between the provided saliency map SM and fixation density map FM. The range of this metric is [-1, 1].

$$CC(SM, FM) = \frac{\sigma(SM, FM)}{\sigma(SM) * \sigma(FM)}$$

ROC curve

ROC curve plots the true-positive rate (TPR) and the false-positive rate (FPR) of a binary classification. For the visual saliency viewpoint, any saliency map can be considered as a group of pixels that can be either salient or not. Some of the pixels are labeled as salient if their value is above a defined threshold and some others are labeled as non-salient if their value is below the threshold. By comparing the saliency map with the given ground truth, the ROC curve of the saliency map is computed by TPR and FPR values at each threshold for n threshold.

Figure .1: An illustration of a ROC curve.

Similarity (SIM)

Similarity metric is a histogram intersection. It measures the similarity between provided saliency maps or fixation density maps. It is calculated as the sum of minimum

values at each pixel of the normalized maps. The range of this metric is $[0, 1]$. Zero means no similarity, one means the same distribution. For saliency map SM and fixation density map FM having n pixels, it is calculated as:

$$SIM(SM, FM) = \sum_i^n \min(SM_i, FM_i) \quad \text{where}$$

$$\sum_i^n SM_i = \sum_i^n FM_i = 1$$